

Figure S1. ARPE-19 and RF/6A cells phenotype in culture. (a) ARPE-19 cells were positive for RPE65 (green). (b) RF/6A cells were positive for lectin (red). Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). Scale bar 20 μ m.

Figure S2. Safety of the delivery of neurotrophins by MSs. (a-e) No TUNEL (red) positive cells were detected in ARPE-19 and RF/6A (f-j) after MSs-E20-80 (c, i), MSs-E40-80 (d, i) and MSs-80 (e, j) treatments compared to saline (a, f). DAPI (blue). Scale bar 20 μ m. n=7-9

Figure S3. Wound healing assay in ARPE-19 and RF/6A. MSs controls did not differ in migration at 24 and 30 h compared with saline in ARPE 19 (a and b, respectively) and RF/6A cells (c and d, respectively). n=7-9